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Research Article

TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT DISRUPTION; ITS PREVALENCE AND SEVERITY OF SYMPTOMS

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Abstract:

Objectives: The objective of this study is to evaluate frequency of temporomandibular joint disorder and its distribution in different age groups among male versus female population.

Study Design: Descriptive cross-sectional study.

Setting: Islamic International Dental Hospital Islamabad, Pakistan.

Period: December 2019 to May 2020.

Material & Method: The study sample comprises of total 140 patients with TMJD, meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Fonseca's questionnaire and Fonseca's Anamnestic Index are employed to assess the subjective response and severity of TMJD symptoms. WHO sample size calculator used to determine sample size. Consecutive sampling technique used. P-value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Results: The results are arranged and statistically evaluated. Overall, 45% answered positive to questions with respect to symptoms. Majority of patients reported positive for neck pain or stiff neck (16%) and muscular fatigue while chewing (17%). 50% of patients suffering from TMJD symptoms belong to Age Group 1 (15 – 35 years). 94.3% female patients suffer from some degree of TMJD. Based on Fonseca's Anamnestic Index of severity, 65.9% of patients have Mild TMJD symptoms, 18.9% with Moderate severity and 1.5% with severe symptoms of TMJD.

Conclusion: This study concludes that TMJD are more common in females with age group of 15 – 35 years of age. The most prevalent symptom is muscular pain / tiredness of jaws during chewing and stiffness of neck. In this study sample, majority of patients suffer from Mild TMJD symptoms

Key words: Anamnestic Index, Fonseca's Questionnaire, Prevalence of TMD, Temporomandibular Joint Disorder

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INTRODUCTION

The temporomandibular joint is the articulation between the lower and upper jaws. The teeth form the contacts between the lower and upper jaws while muscles move the mandible.¹Temporo-Mandibular Joint Disorders cause pain in the jaws and / or surrounding muscles, leading to significant pain, distress and functional disturbance / limitations.² TMJD is the most prevailing musculoskeletal condition after chronic low back pain. For clinical and research settings, current diagnostic criteria for Temporomandibular Disorders (DC/TMD)³ defines 12 common TMD including but not limited to Arthralgia, Myalgia Local Myalgia, Myofascial pain, Myofascial pain with referral, four-disc displacement disorders, Degenerative joint disease, Subluxation and Headache attributed to TMD.^{4,5}

Common symptoms present in patients of TMD are toothache, facial pain, TMJ joint sounds, earache and limited jaw movements. Often these patients present in dental clinics with complain of toothache because they naturally assume that tooth is causing the problem. Consequently, it is imperative for the dentist to recognize these patients, diagnose the actual cause of the symptoms, ascertain their needs and select appropriate treatment / intervention options.^{6,7} The etiology of TMJD is fairly complex and multifactorial, including structural abnormalities of TMJ, stress induced muscle hyperactivity and overuse of joint.⁸ In 1973, a research study proposed four (4) foremost theories underlying the etiology of temporomandibular disorders (TMDs), whereby two of these were psychological and psychophysiological.^{8,9} Diagnosis of TMJD is carried out by evaluating patients' history with subsequent physical examination.¹⁰ Additionally, diagnostic TMJ imaging methods provide an assessment of TMJ components' integrity and their functional association which confirm the extent and/ or progression of existing disease.¹¹ These disorders are most common among the 20-45 years age group with an increasing tendency in female gender. Following are the symptoms of temporomandibular joint syndrome.¹²

MATERIAL & METHODS:

This is a cross-sectional study carried out at Islamic International Dental Hospital Islamabad, Pakistan from December 2019 to May 2020. The study sample comprises of total 140 patients meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Sample size was calculated using WHO sample size formula. Patients were selected using consecutive sampling technique. Along with patient history, a thorough clinical examination is

carried out to establish the prevalence and severity of temporomandibular joint disorders using Fonseca's Questionnaire and Fonseca's Anamnestic Index (IAF). Patients are categorized on basis of presenting symptoms and frequencies for various categorical variables like gender, age group etc are calculated.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients of both genders with age ranging from 15 to 70 years.
- All patients diagnosed with TMD having symptoms of pain, clicking and limited mouth opening.
- Patients who have previously received treatment for TMDs.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with organic dental disease and other disorders which may mimic TMJD pain.
- Patients with bone diseases like Osteoporosis, osteopetrosis- or osteomalacia.
- Patients with debilitating diseases including rheumatoid arthritis, poliomyelitis- or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.
- Patients with neurological disease including Dyskinesia (Abnormality in performing voluntary muscle movements Female patients with pregnancy.
- Patients with any previous history of Orthodontic treatment, Cleft surgery or Orthognathic surgery.

Data Collection Procedure

A detailed history is obtained from each patient based on Fonseca's Questionnaire (Table-I). Follow-on oral examination is carried out to evaluate and rule out any other organic or dental condition which may mimic symptoms of TMD.

Patients are assessed on basis of symptoms such as facial pain, TMJ tenderness, locking / stiffness or tenderness of jaw muscles, joint sounds, limitations in mandibular movement and difficulty in chewing. Patients presenting with one or more of these symptoms are included in the study. The severity is assessed and diagnosis of type of TMD is carried out using Fonseca's Anamnestic Index (IAF) . Data collected from patients is entered in SPSS ® version 16.0 for statistical analysis.

RESULTS:

Total 140 cases were studied. Age range of the patients was 15-68 years with mean age of 35.4 ± 5.7 years. There were 50% cases between age 15-35 years, 27% between 36-50 years and 22.8% between 51-70 years.

There were 39.3% male and 60.7% female cases. Overall 54% answered positive to questions with respect to symptoms. Majority of patients reported positive for neck pain or stiff neck (35.7%) and

muscular fatigue while chewing (50%). Difficulty in opening mouth was noticed in 7.1% cases, difficulty in moving mandible in 12.1% and clenching of teeth was reported in 15.7% cases.

Table-I: Age distribution of study cases

Age Group	Age (Years)	Frequency of Patients
1	15–35	70 (50.0%)
2	36–50	38 (27.1%)
3	51–70	32 (22.8%)

Table-II: Age distribution among male and female cases

Gender	Age group			Total
	1	2	3	
Male	30	10	15	55
Female	40	25	20	85

Table-III: Frequency of patient's response to the questionnaire

Question	Yes	No	Sometimes
Is it difficult for you to open your mouth?	10 (7.1%)	121 (86.4%)	09 (6.4%)
Is it difficult for you to move mandible from side to side?	17 (12.1%)	100 (71.4%)	23 (16.4%)
Do you get tired or have pain during chewing food?	70 (50%)	45 (32.1%)	25 (17.8%)
Do you have recurrent headaches?	48 (34.3%)	62 (44.2%)	30 (21.4%)
Do you have any pain on the nape or stiff neck?	50 (35.7%)	40 (28.6%)	50 (35.7%)
Do you have recurrent earaches or pain in craniomandibular joints?	36 (25.7%)	64 (45.7%)	40 (28.6%)
Have you noticed any TMJ clicking when you open your mouth or during chewing?	33 (23.6%)	77 (55%)	30 (21.4%)
Do you clench or grind your teeth?	22 (15.7%)	92 (65.7%)	26 (18.6%)
Do you feel your teeth do not articulate well?	18 (12.8%)	122 (87.1%)	10 (7.1%)
Do you consider yourself an anxious / nervous / tense patient?	45 (32.1%)	65 (46.5%)	30 (21.4%)

Based on Fonseca's Anamnestic Index of severity, 70% of patients have Mild TMJD symptoms, 13% with moderate severity and 2% with severe symptoms of TMJD, while 15% cases were having no symptoms at all.

Figure-I: Severity of TMJD among study cases

DISCUSSION:

This cross-sectional descriptive study carried out amongst the patients visiting Islamic International Dental Hospital Islamabad, Pakistan, provides an outline of prevalence of TMD's symptoms in Islamabad. This study is to evaluate the presence of TMDs symptoms which are often misdiagnosed by inexperienced dental clinicians. In this study, 54 % answers are positive for subjective symptoms based on "Yes" and "Sometimes", while Agerberg and Carlsson¹⁶ and Szentpetery *et al*¹³ found that 57% and 20.6% patients have reported subjective symptoms respectively. The results of this study suggest overwhelming female predilection which corroborate the previous finding of Pedroni *et al*,¹⁴ Garcia *et al*,¹⁵ and Otuyemi *et al*.¹⁶ Nevertheless, it is recommended that a detailed clinical examination and mental health assessment of female patients in these settings be carried out to elicit reasons of high prevalence in female gender.

Nomura *et al* had found that 35.78% of patients have mild TMJD, 11.93% of patients had moderate TMJD and 5.5% of patients had severe TMJD.¹⁷ Wänman and Agerberg had determined that 13% and 7% patients had moderate and severe TMJD respectively.¹⁸ Yet another study conducted by Rieder *et al* had determined that 10.3% individuals suffered from advanced and severe TMJD.¹⁹ Although the results of this study corroborate with previous findings, it further establishes that mild TMJD is 70%, moderate TMJD

is 13% and severe TMJD is only 2% , while no disease found in 15% cases. This can be explained by the fact that people in rural areas are inherently having little rest due extensive manual work in agricultural fields. Other reason could be inability of clinicians to diagnose initial concealed symptoms which can be prevented from further aggressiveness.

With respect to gender, the results of this study, 94.3%, corroborate the findings of Garcia *et al*, Solberg *et al*, Shiau and Chang.²⁰ Higher prevalence of signs associated with mandibular disorder have been reported in female gender in these studies. The higher prevalence of women diagnosed with some degree of TMD may be related to physiologic differences in female

CONCLUSION:

This study concludes that TMJD are more common in females with age group of 15 – 35 years of age. The most prevalent symptom is muscular pain / tiredness of jaws during chewing and stiffness of neck. In this study sample, majority of patients suffer from Mild TMJD symptoms.

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